

Sectoral brief

November 2025

Reducing Risks Together: Multi-hazards and multi-risks in the transport sector

Executive summary & Recommendations

Transport infrastructure is the lifeblood of modern society but often struggles to meet demands and expectations on reliability, availability, maintainability, safety, environment, health and cost. It is increasingly vulnerable to a range of natural hazards, including floods, earthquakes, storms, etc which have the potential to disrupt transport systems, damage infrastructure, and cause significant economic losses.

While the focus in the transport sector has been on climate change adaptation for transportation infrastructure, it is essential to adopt a more comprehensive and systemic approach to risk management.

MYRIAD-EU's vision is to catalyse the paradigm shift required to move towards a multi-risk, multi-sector, systemic approach to risk assessment and management. To achieve this vision, our overall aim is that by the end of MYRIAD-EU policy-makers, decision-makers, and practitioners will be able to develop forward-looking disaster risk management pathways that assess trade-offs and synergies across sectors, hazards, and scales.

Recommendations:

- **Implement Integrated Risk Assessment Models:** The multi-hazard risk assessment tools developed by MYRIAD-EU should be adopted. This will help to better understand vulnerabilities and inform investment decisions.

- **Develop Cross-Sectoral Collaboration:** Cooperation between sectors (e.g. transport, energy etc) should be encouraged to ensure a more coordinated response to extreme weather and other multi-hazard events.

- **Establish Real-Time Data Sharing Mechanisms:** Roll out integrated decision-support systems like the one developed by MYRIAD-EU to improve real-time coordination during multi-hazard events, enhancing the efficiency and speed of response.

- **Prioritise Infrastructure Resilience:** Critical infrastructure that are at high risk can be identified through MYRIAD-EU's risk assessment models. This will help in their upgrade and reinforcement (e.g. bridges, tunnels, and rail lines) to withstand extreme weather and other hazards.

Context

In early August 2023, major floods resulting in landslides occurred in approximately two-thirds of the territory of Slovenia due to heavy rain. In the aftermath of the disaster, it was established that over 60 bridges of various spans were damaged or destroyed. As reported, the disaster stands as the largest in the history of the country. Three months after the flooding, heavy rain struck Slovenia again with a total of more than 300 litres per square meter of rainfall recorded in some areas. Compounding the situation, the soil remained saturated from the intense rains in August. This combination of factors resulted in numerous landslides and elevated water levels, leading to significant damage to both infrastructure and houses in the region.

The transport sector is exposed to a range of interconnected hazards, which makes the assessment of multi-hazard risk very important. This will enable decision-makers to anticipate and mitigate the impacts of simultaneous or cascading events, ensuring that infrastructure, operations, and safety measures are designed to withstand multiple threats. By adopting this comprehensive risk assessment, the sector can improve resilience, minimise disruptions, and protect both economic interests and public safety.

The MYRIAD-EU project is designed to address the aforementioned challenges. Our vision is to catalyse the paradigm shift required to move towards a multi-risk, multi-sector, systemic approach to risk assessment and management. To achieve this, the overall aim is to develop forward-looking disaster risk reduction pathways in five Pilot EU regions: Danube, Scandinavia, North Sea, Veneto, Canary Islands. Within these Pilots, we assess trade-offs and synergies of various strategies across sectors. These sectors are energy, ecosystems & forestry, finance, food & agriculture, tourism, and transport & infrastructure. Within the project, we develop tools and methods to allow us to better assess multi-hazard-risk within these sectors. The project is funded by Horizon 2020 and runs between 2021-2025.

Applications of MYRIAD-EU results

1. MYRIAD-EU Multi-Risk Toolkit

The toolkit comprises core analytical modules including the Curve Explorer, Exposure at Risk, Scenario Calculator, Scenario Showcase, and the Vulnerability Index Editor (Daniell et al., 2025). These allow users to visualise vulnerability functions, assess sectoral exposure, simulate risk under concurrent or sequential hazards, and generate spatial vulnerability indices. These tools could potentially help transport agencies evaluate

potential vulnerabilities across various hazard scenarios as well as being used by national and regional transport authorities to identify high-risk areas and prioritise infrastructure upgrades, such as reinforcing bridges.

Figure 1 MYRIAD-EU Multi-Risk Toolkit front screen

The most relevant module to the transport sector could potentially be the Scenario Showcase, which is also one of the core modules in the Toolkit. It provides users with the ability to estimate potential losses by integrating hazard intensity maps, spatial exposure datasets, and associated vulnerability functions. This simulation tool is essential for decision-makers and risk analysts aiming to quantify economic and physical damages under hypothetical or observed hazard scenarios. Some of the ways the transport sector will benefit from the Scenario Showcase is in the identification of vulnerabilities, risk prioritisation as well as the possibility of developing more effective, resilient infrastructure and emergency response plans through integrated risk assessment and planning.

2. MYRIAD-HESA (MYRIAD – Hazard Event Sets Algorithm)

MYRIAD-HESA is a fully open-access method that can create multi-hazard event sets from any hazard events that occur on varying time, space, and intensity scales (Claassen et al., 2023). This is then used to generate the first global multi-hazard event set database (MYRIAD-HES). This database demonstrates how frequently multi-hazards of varying combinations occur, and where their hotspots are located, while accounting for different time-lags in between hazards.

The MYRIAD-HES dataset incorporates historic single-hazard events data (including geophysical, meteorological, hydrological, and climatological hazards) collected from various sources with an overlapping timespan from 2004 to 2017. MYRIAD-HESA allows governments to plan for specific multi-hazard events and provide insights into the number of overlapping events they need to account for. NGOs can consider the information on locations of global hotspots that are susceptible to multi-hazards to prioritise the allocation of (future) resources.

For the road transport sector, the tool can be used to evaluate the vulnerability of roads, highways, and related infrastructure to a variety of hazards, including natural hazards (such as earthquakes, floods, landslides, and storms) and man-made threats (such as accidents, terrorism, or sabotage). Transport stakeholders that could benefit from the tool include:

- National or regional governments: For infrastructure planning, disaster management, and climate adaptation.
- Transport authorities and operators: For route optimisation, risk mitigation strategies, and operational planning.
- Consultants and engineers: For designing and reinforcing transport infrastructure.

Recommendations

- **Implement Integrated Risk Assessment Models:** The multi-hazard risk assessment tools developed by MYRIAD-EU should be adopted. This will help to better understand vulnerabilities and inform investment decisions.

Intended stakeholders: transport agencies and infrastructure planners.

- **Develop Cross-Sectoral Collaboration:** Cooperation between sectors (e.g. transport, energy etc) should be encouraged to ensure a more coordinated response to extreme weather and other multi-hazard events.

Intended stakeholders: national and regional transport authorities.

- **Establish Real-Time Data Sharing Mechanisms:** Roll out integrated decision-support systems like the one developed by MYRIAD-EU to improve real-time coordination during multi-hazard events, enhancing the efficiency and speed of response.

Intended stakeholders: transport operators and emergency services.

- **Prioritise Infrastructure Resilience:** Critical infrastructure that are at high risk can be identified through the MYRIAD-EU's risk assessment models. This will help in their upgrade and reinforcement (e.g. bridges, tunnels, and rail lines) to withstand extreme weather and other hazards.

Intended stakeholders: infrastructure managers and local governments.

List of resources

References

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